

Profiling structure–mechanical heterogeneity of PAN carbon fiber along radius direction

Lifeng Hao, Ping Peng, Weicheng Jiao, Rongguo Wang, Xiaodong, He
Center for Composite Materials and Structures, Harbin Institute of Technology,
Harbin, 150080, China
E-mail address: hlf@hit.edu.cn

Abstract:

We report the study of the correlation between the structure and mechanical property of T700 carbon fiber monofilaments via radius profiling. It is found that, the maximum of the modulus is at a radius of 1.8 μm , instead of at the surface as usually assumed.

Carbon fibers (CFs) are important structural materials widely used in many fields, such as aerospace and aircraft industry. It is well known that CF monofilament possesses heterogeneous skin–core structure, which causes nonuniform stress distribution, concentrating stress in certain regions, accelerating the formation and the growth of microvoids, and eventually leading to fracture. Therefore, it is of prime importance to measure the structure and the mechanical properties of monofilament simultaneously with high spatial resolution. Although previous methods (wide-angle X-ray diffraction, small-angle X-ray scattering, micro-Raman spectrum, et al.) gave fruitful information, they all have some limitations. In this work, we present a study of the structure–mechanical heterogeneity of polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based carbon fibers (CFs) via a new method, named as radius profiling, developed in our group. With the method, the radius distribution of the structure and mechanical properties of CF monofilament were measured with a spatial resolution as high as 10nm. CF monofilaments were peeled layer by layer by plasma etching, and their electrical resistances and mechanical properties were measured by a multimeter and a single-filament tensile tester, respectively. The morphologies of the original and the etched CFs as etching time increased are shown in figure 1. The radius of the CF decreases with the increase in the etching time and drops to 1 μm without breaking. It is clear that plasma etching is capable of removing the outermost materials of monofilament continuously until the core part is exposed, enabling radius profiling to measure the inner properties of CFs. In addition, it was found that the surface gets rougher as the etching time increases, showing pits and bumps with increased dimensions and density, particularly for CF with a diameter etched to less than 2.5 μm . The relationship between the structure and the mechanical properties of the CF monofilament indicates that structure and the mechanical properties distributions possess similar dependence on radius position, revealing a strong correlation. Unlike the simple skin–core model in which only the difference between the core and skin region was considered, the distribution of crystallinity, and that of modulus, varies continuously from surface to core and shows fine structures in both surface and core regions. It was noted that the maximums of crystallinity and modulus do not appear at the outmost surface, where the graphitization process starts. From the crystallinity distribution, it is noted that the surface stress was lower than that inside because the stress tends to concentrate in the high-modulus region. Numerical simulation

was also carried out by Ansys to determine the stress distribution along the radius directions and it was found that the stress in the high modulus region was about 1.8 times of that at surface. This effectively explains why Pan carbon fibers possess high strength, because under tensile loading the surface region where fracture normally initialized is less stressed.

Figure 1 SEM images of Pan carbon fiber monofilament during plasma etching.

Figure 2 (a) Measured modulus and crystallinity distribution along radius directions. (b) Strain distribution and (c) stress distribution in the numerical simulation